

Title: Removing Structural Barriers to an Inclusive and Just Low-Carbon Transport Transition in Low- and Middle-Income Countries

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Summary

Decarbonising the transport sector is fundamental to delivering on national climate commitments and advancing the global ambition of sustainable development. However, the expansion of low-carbon transport does not automatically translate into improved outcomes for all. Multiple structural barriers continue to prevent vulnerable people and persons with disabilities from benefiting equally from the low-carbon transport transition. Barriers to inclusive transport include limited physical access [1], affordability constraints [2], and shortcomings in infrastructure and technology [3], which risk being reinforced in the design and deployment of low-carbon systems. These challenges result from transport systems that optimise for technical or efficiency metrics yet fail to embed social inclusion in their design. A persistent disconnect thus remains between stated policy ambitions, such as delivering inclusive transport infrastructure, enhancing safety, and expanding access, and the realities of implementation on the ground. Addressing these constraints is essential to ensure that transport infrastructure is not only low-carbon but also inclusive, equitable, and just. Following a systematic academic and grey literature review, this policy brief examines the barriers to inclusive low-carbon transport in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs).

Key Policy Recommendations

- Mainstream disability perspectives throughout the policy design and planning process, where persons with disabilities are actively engaged in shaping priorities, identifying barriers, and co-developing solutions.
- Introduce temporary exemptions from emissions charges to prevent persons with disabilities from facing increased financial exclusion under low-emission and traffic restriction policies when accessible alternatives are unavailable.
- Embed accessibility for persons with disabilities into the planning and delivery of low-carbon transport systems, including infrastructure design, technological interfaces, and information provision.
- Expand research and collect disaggregated data on persons with disabilities to ensure that low-carbon transport planning reflects diverse needs and reduces exclusion.

Introduction

Persons with disabilities represent a significant share of the global population, with an estimated 1.3 billion individuals (around 16% worldwide) having some form of disability [4]. This proportion is projected to grow further as global populations age. Much of this population (80%) resides in LMICs, where structural disadvantages, including poverty and inadequate infrastructure, often reinforce existing forms of marginalisation [4,5]. Without the correct support, this can lead to lower labour market participation, reduced educational attainment, and poorer health outcomes, creating cumulative effects that entrench long-term socioeconomic disadvantage [4]. Inadequate and poorly designed transport infrastructure further compounds these challenges by creating physical obstacles that limits independent mobility for persons with disabilities [6]. Any transition towards sustainable transport

systems that fails to explicitly address equity risks can therefore deepen existing disparities by reinforcing unequal access to employment, essential services, and mobility for marginalised groups.

While the concept of a “just transition” has gained political traction, actual transition policies continue to problematically conflate equity with equality to the detriment of persons with disabilities. A just transition requires that climate action prioritises fairness and inclusion by generating shared prosperity while avoiding the marginalisation of vulnerable groups. It must leverage the economic and social gains of decarbonisation to redistribute benefits and support those least able to adapt while proactively addressing its challenges and impacts through inclusive dialogue with affected communities [7]. However, many transport and infrastructure transition policies, from electric vehicle (EV) subsidies to active travel schemes, continue to be developed on the implicit assumption of able-bodied users with equal access to physical infrastructure, financial resources, and a full range of mobility options. This overlooks the barriers faced by persons with disabilities, for example inaccessible or disrupted pavements, as well as significant gaps in awareness and understanding of inclusive design among policymakers, particularly in relation to the needs of persons with disabilities.

Despite often being understood as a physical, mental, or sensory impairment, disability arises when a person with such an impairment does not have equal access to and benefit from opportunities due to social, attitudinal, physical, and environmental constraints [6,8]. While definitions of disability generally convey similar underlying meaning, they differ in emphasis, terminology, and conceptual framing. Some approaches are rooted in medical perspectives, while others reflect social or rights-based understandings or a combination of the two¹ [9]. To ensure consistency, the definition set out in the United Nations (UN) Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (CRPD) was applied in the research underlying this brief:

“Persons with disabilities include those who have long-term physical, mental, intellectual or sensory impairments which in interaction with various barriers may hinder their full and effective participation in society on an equal basis with others.” [10]

Although persons with disabilities represent a significant share of the population in LMICs, their needs and perspectives remain largely marginalised in energy and low-carbon transport policy formulation and decision-making processes [11]. Evidence from LMICs highlights that current infrastructure frequently excludes persons with disabilities [6]. Overall, this constrains their mobility and participation, often leaving them reliant on costly, carbon-intensive motorised transport [12]. That existing infrastructure has consistently failed persons with disabilities makes the stakes of the low-carbon transition all the higher. The transition to sustainable transport offers a critical opportunity to embed accessibility as a core design requirement and avoid entrenching existing inequalities.

¹ Medical models treat disability as an individual deficit, while rights-based approaches locate disability in social, environmental, and institutional barriers. This shift matters because it redirects policy from individual adaptation towards structural accessibility and inclusion.

Methodology

In March 2025, the Gender Equality and Social Inclusion (GESI) Unit of the Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) Programme organised a scoping workshop in Nairobi, bringing together disability advocates and researchers, many of whom were persons with disabilities themselves, aimed at understanding how disability inclusion in energy and transport transitions can be enhanced. The participants spanned across Ghana, Kenya, Malawi and Zambia. The participants unanimously identified the absence of documented evidence on disability inclusion and energy transitions, a phenomenon that continues to limit both their advocacy and the required intervention.

It is against this backdrop that we conducted a systematic academic and grey literature review to synthesise the ‘state of play’ of disability inclusion in the energy transition, including the barriers to disability inclusion in the low-carbon transport transition. Much of the existing knowledge base relies on case studies from high-income countries (HICs), reflecting a structural gap in global disability and transport research.

Evidence drawn from HIC contexts was systematically reviewed and filtered according to its transferability to the conditions and constraints characteristic of LMICs. Although the contexts differ, the challenges identified and the policy responses proposed provide transferable insights that can be adapted to support more inclusive low-carbon transition pathways in LMICs.

Barriers to Low-Carbon Transport for Persons with Disabilities in LMICs

1. Transport Access and Affordability

Inaccessible public transport systems restrict mobility for persons with disabilities and often compel them to rely on private motorised transport (i.e., privately-owned cars) [3]. These are both more expensive and more polluting [6], as while electrification is central to transport decarbonisation the high upfront cost of EVs remains a significant financial barrier for many households [8]. Where both public transport and privately-owned vehicles are inaccessible, persons with disabilities often depend on costly door-to-door and taxi services as their only viable means of mobility [13]. Poorly designed low-carbon transport policies risk limiting or eliminating taxi services, effectively removing the last accessible modes of travel for persons who are already structurally marginalised.

Persons with disabilities are more likely to experience energy poverty and persistent financial constraints [14], which can reduce household budgets for transport and limit mobility options. Assuming lower energy use risks obscuring their mobility needs and leading to exclusionary low-carbon transport policies. Additional costs associated with the transition, such as EV adoption or Low-Emission Zones (LEZs), may further compound these constraints [8]. These outcomes are not incidental, as planning, financing, and governance systems often reproduce inequity by default [15] unless inclusion is explicitly embedded in policy design and implementation.

As cities pursue low-carbon transport transitions, LEZs have become an increasingly prominent policy tool for improving urban air quality and driving the uptake of clean private

vehicles [8]. Yet their introduction risks creating new barriers to mobility for vulnerable populations, particularly persons with disabilities [16]. Where the private vehicle represents the only viable means of travel, LEZ charges risk imposing a disproportionate financial burden on disabled travellers already facing a transport system deficient in meeting their needs, creating a dual penalty [2,8]. Critically, spatial proximity to city centres cannot be taken as a proxy for accessibility or the feasibility of different transport options to choose from, as a substitute for personal motorised vehicles. For many persons with disabilities, neither active travel nor public transport constitutes a realistic alternative, regardless of distance [16]. Policy interventions premised on the assumption that residents can simply switch modes of transport overlook the extent to which different kinds of impairments fundamentally shape, and in many cases rule out, the available options. Dedicated policy attention and targeted support options are therefore required to address the needs of persons with disabilities [15], with assessments of transition readiness grounded in lived experiences of disability rather than geographic indicators alone.

2. Infrastructure and Technology Accessibility

Low-carbon transport infrastructure and technology development have proceeded largely without meaningful consideration of disabled persons' access needs [17]. As an example, the lack of private parking or garage space prevents many households from installing home charging facilities, limiting their ability to adopt EVs [8] - a much more feasible option for many persons with disabilities than active or public transport, as discussed above. Public charging infrastructure, which is projected to significantly expand in response to LEZs and climate policies, particularly in HICs, can disproportionately affect persons with disabilities, who may face greater difficulty travelling to charging points, navigating congested spaces, and accessing charging infrastructure independently. As LMICs invest in scaling up charging infrastructure, early integration of accessibility considerations can help avoid the replication of barriers observed in HIC settings.

The design of low-carbon infrastructure itself is also problematic for many with disabilities [18]. For example, charging infrastructure can pose practical barriers, including limited ability to apply force due to connector angles, as well as difficulties handling heavy cables and overhead movements, particularly for those with upper-limb impairments or wheelchair users [1]. Similarly, modifying electric wheelchair-accessible vehicles (WAVs) frequently involves design trade-offs that can reduce interior space, including headroom, and degrade the overall travel experience [8,19]. Furthermore, both public and private services linked to low-carbon transport and infrastructure frequently lack essential accessibility requirements and assistive technologies, ranging from step-free boarding access to basic facilities such as accessible toilets, creating everyday physical barriers that cannot be navigated by persons with certain impairments [6].

One of the key barriers to progress is the lack of a shared, operational definition of 'accessibility' that reflects the diverse needs of persons with disabilities [1]. Globally, accessible charging design standards remain largely absent [18], highlighting a systemic gap in low-carbon transport transition policy coordination and technical frameworks. When these systemic design failures persist, they contribute to the deepening of socio-economic

exclusion, reinforcing unequal access to opportunities, services, and participation in society [12].

Emerging evidence from HICs points to the transformative potential of connected autonomous vehicles (CAVs) [20] and shared micromobility [21] for certain disabled users, including individuals with physical impairments, chronic health conditions, and cognitive or neurodiverse differences. For instance, CAVs can provide users with physical and sensory impairments with safety and independence [20]. Similarly, shared micromobility, including e-scooters and e-bikes, is often a more accessible and empowering option than walking for many individuals with physical disabilities [22]. Systemic inaccessibility, both in the physical design of these vehicles and in the digital interfaces through which services are accessed, continues to exclude a significant proportion of persons with disabilities. Barriers include difficulties with boarding, mounting, and manoeuvring these vehicles, limited availability of appropriate assistive features, and digital booking platforms that are incompatible with assistive technologies, alongside low awareness of available options among potential users [20,21,23]. Beyond access barriers, the expansion of CAVs and shared micromobility services introduces a separate set of safety risks for persons with disabilities [24]. Characteristics inherent to these e-vehicles, including minimal noise output, design issues, and variable operating speeds can render shared street environments significantly more hazardous, particularly for those with sensory or mobility impairments [2,20,23,25]

Conclusion and Policy Recommendations

Ensuring equitable outcomes demands rigorous assessment of who may be left behind when access restrictions are not considered. As the shift toward electric mobility accelerates, accessibility must be treated as a foundational design requirement rather than a subsequent retrofit consideration. In response, the following policy recommendations have been identified:

1. Engagement and co-creation

Low-carbon transport systems must be designed to accommodate the wide range of needs and lived experiences of persons with different impairments. Integrating persons with disabilities into decision-making structures at all levels and actively engaging them as co-creators is essential to ensure that low-carbon transport systems are shaped by inclusive and representative perspectives [11,24]. This requires formalising participatory procedures within policy design, planning, and governance processes and recognising lived experience as a form of expertise [26,27].

2. Affordability: Exemptions from emission charges and Low Emission Zones

When public transport remains inaccessible, the introduction of high-emission charges on private internal combustion engine vehicles can place a disproportionate burden on persons with disabilities, compounding existing barriers beyond their control. As part of an inclusive low-carbon transition, transport measures should incorporate exemptions or flexible compliance for vehicles used by persons with disabilities within LEZs [8]. National and local governments should support a fair vehicle transition by providing targeted scrappage schemes and financial incentives for persons with disabilities to enable a transition to accessible low-

emission vehicles [8], given that for many persons with disabilities driving is not a choice but a necessity enabling access to essential services such as healthcare and social support. The decarbonisation of shared mobility services should be used as an opportunity to expand rather than restrict accessible travel options and to ensure that existing mobility options are not reduced for persons with disabilities. This requires maintaining access within low-traffic areas or vehicle-restricted zones, while also supporting affordable fleets of clean energy WAVs within shared mobility services, particularly for those who continue to rely on private or door-to-door transport to meet essential needs [8].

3. Accessible design and infrastructure

Decarbonising transport systems requires both increased use of public transport and greater participation in active modes of travel [24]. Accessibility for persons with disabilities must be embedded across the full lifecycle of energy and low-carbon transport systems, extending beyond physical infrastructure to include policy design, service delivery, digital platforms, and governance frameworks [1,27] Systemic change requires that governments and public authorities embed accessibility standards within transport and energy policies, strengthening institutional capacity on inclusive design, and ensuring accessibility is integrated across planning, procurement, and implementation processes. As accessible infrastructure and services become established, low-carbon micromobility solutions, such as adapted e-scooters or e-bikes, can offer an additional mobility pathway for some persons with disabilities, further expanding access to affordable, low-emission transport options. Moreover, when pedestrian infrastructure is designed to be inclusive, persons with disabilities are less likely to rely on private motorised vehicles for short journeys, supporting lower-energy mobility options [12]. At the same time, the related digital transformation must be inclusive by design. Platform developers should ensure that booking applications, payment systems, and service platforms should be accessible and user-friendly for persons with different impairments and compatible with other assistive technologies, ensuring that digitalisation does not create new barriers to access [28].

4. Research and data

Research and policy processes continue to give insufficient attention to disability inclusion in the low-carbon transport transition in both HICs and LMICs. Despite the fact that majority of persons with disabilities live in LMICs, there remains a significant lack of data, including disability-disaggregated data for transport planning, and context-specific case studies examining disability within low-carbon transition processes in these settings. This evidence gap constrains the ability to design, target, and evaluate inclusive energy and transport interventions. As such, it is crucial to expand disability data and research to inform inclusive low-carbon transition planning, particularly in LMICs.

Transport decarbonisation strategies need to be designed to ensure they are accessible and inclusive, rather than reinforcing existing inequalities. Yet in LMICs, the evidence base required to understand and remove the barriers remains insufficient. The dependence of this brief on HIC evidence, which is also underrepresented in the existing literature, is a significant methodological limitation, but one that unquestionably points to the critical importance of gathering LMIC data to underpin evidence-based inclusive decision-making

and achieve systemic change. Climate-driven investment and shift towards low-carbon transport systems must not come at the cost of inclusivity, as infrastructure that cannot be used by persons with disabilities fails on both equity and effectiveness grounds.

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